

Terpenoids: Part. XXXVIII.

A new approach towards the synthesis of (\pm) Angustione

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A facile synthesis of 4 : 4 : 6-trimethyl-cyclohexane-1 : 3-dione easily convertible to (\pm)-Angustione has been accomplished through an application of modified Wittig reaction.

The cyclohexane:1 : 3-dione derivative, angustione which occurs in the essential oil of *Bacchousia angustifolia* was studied several years ago by Simonsen and Coworkers^{1,2} and later on by Birch³ who proposed the expression (I) for the ketone on the basis of its chemical properties. The revised structure was confirmed by spectral data³ and syntheses⁴⁻⁶.

4 : 4 : 6-Trimethyl-1 : 3-dione (II) is the key intermediate that has been employed for the synthesis of (\pm)-angustione by various workers⁴⁻⁶. However, the methods used for its preparations are circuitous and complicated. In the present communication, we report a new approach to the diketone (II) through modified Wittig reaction on a properly substituted aldehyde with the ethyl- α -diethylphosphonopropionate. The various steps in the synthesis are as under :—

Ethyl 2 : 2 dimethyl-3, 3-ethylenedioxybutanoate (IV) secured through ketalisation of ethyl 2 : 2 dimethyl-3-oxobutanoate (III), under Salmi's technique⁷, on being subjected to lithium aluminium hydride reduction furnished 2 : 2 dimethyl-3, 3-ethylenedioxy-butan-1-ol(V) in 81.2% yield. The carbinol (V) was oxidised with chromic acid in pyridine⁸, smoothly

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till no more water collected in the limb. Thereafter, the contents were cooled, PTS was destroyed with 5% solution of sodiumbicarbonate, washed the reaction mixture with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After the removal of the solvent, the residue on distillation under reduced pressure gave the ketal (IV), b.p. $120^{\circ}/15$ mm, yield 21.9 g. (82.2%), $^{35}\eta_D$ 1.4300. I.R. spectrum : 1050 cm^{-1} (ketal), $1380, 1460\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 1720 cm^{-1} (ester). Found : C, 59.49; H, 8.90; Calc. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$: C, 59.38; H, 8.97.

2,2-Dimethyl-3,3-(ethylene-dioxyethyl)-butan-1-ol (V) : To a fine suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (2.8 g.) in anhydrous ether (200 ml.) was added the above ketal ester (IV) (20.0 g.) in ether (75 ml.) at such a rate so as to maintain ether at a gentle reflux. The reaction mixture after being stirred and refluxed for another 3 hrs was cooled and decomposed with saturated solution of sodium sulphate and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent expelled. The residual oil was distilled under vacuum to yield the alcohol (V), b.p. $100-102^{\circ}/5-6$ mm, yield (13.0 g., 81.2%), $^{35}\eta_D$ 1.4470. I.R. spectrum : 3450 cm^{-1} ($-\text{OH}$), $1460, 1380\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$) 1050 cm^{-1} (Broad band $-\text{OH}$ and ketal). Found : C, 59.79; H, 9.90; Calc. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$: C, 59.98; H, 10.07.

2,2-Dimethyl-3,3-(ethylenedioxyethyl)-butanol (VI) : A solution of 12 g. of the above ketal carbinol (V) in (80 ml.) of anhydrous pyridine was added to a solution of (14.2 g.) of chromic acid in pyridine (240 ml.). The mixture was thoroughly shaken and allowed to stand at room temperature for 3 hrs. Thereafter, it was poured into ice cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with brine solution and sodium hydroxide solution (2%) and again with water. After drying, the solvent was stripped off. The residual oil on distillation under diminished pressure furnished (9.0 g., 75%) the aldehyde (VI) as a colourless oil b.p. $90-95^{\circ}/7$ mm. $^{35}\eta_D$ 1.4485 I.R. spectrum : $2725, 1705\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($-\text{CHO}$), 1050 cm^{-1} (ketal), $1460, 1380\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$). Found : C, 60.85; H, 9.05; Calc. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$: C, 60.74; H, 8.86.

Ethyl-2, 4, 4-trimethyl-5, 5-(ethylenedioxyethyl) hex-2-ene-1-oate (VII) : A slurry of sodium hydride (2.93 g.) was prepared in diethylene glycol dimethyl ether (140 ml.) and ethyl- α -diethyl-phosphonopropionate (18.3 g.) was added dropwise at room temperature. After the addition, the solution was stirred until the evolution of the gas had ceased. To the resultant yellow solution, was then added, the aldehyde (VI) (8.0 g.) slowly below 0° . After the addition, the solution was stirred for 3 hrs. and then refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The product was extracted with ether after decomposing with excess of water and then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After the removal of the solvent, the residue on distillation under reduced pressure gave (7.0 g., 75.9%) ethyl-2, 4, 4-trimethyl-5, 5-(ethylenedioxyethyl)-hex-2-ene-1-oate (VII); b.p. $145^{\circ}/5$ mm. $^{35}\eta_D$ 1.4500. I.R. spectrum : 1710 cm^{-1} (α - β -unsaturated ester) $1458, 1376\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 1045 cm^{-1} (ketal), 960 cm^{-1} (trans double bond). Found : C, 64.32; H, 9.05; Calc. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4$: C, 64.44; H, 9.15.

Ethyl-5, 5-(ethyldioxyethyl)-4, 4, 2-trimethyl hexanoate (VIII) : Hydrogenation of the unsaturated ester (VII) was carried out at the initial pressure of 30 lbs., dissolved in ethanol (100 ml.) in the presence of palladised charcoal (10%). The reduction was completed in 15 hrs. The catalyst was filtered off and the solvent removed. The residue was distilled

to afford the saturated ketal ester (VIII), yield (6.5 g.) (93%), b.p. $140^{\circ}/5$ mm., $^{35}\eta_D$ 1.4540. I.R. spectrum : 1730 cm^{-1} (ester), $1458, 1376\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 1045 cm^{-1} (ketal). Found : C, 63.99; H, 10.20; Calc. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4$: C, 63.93; H, 9.83.

Ethyl-2, 4, 4-trimethyl-1-acetyl-butanoate (IX) : To a solution of the ketal ester (VIII) (3.8 g.) in acetone (50 ml.) was added hydrochloric acid (20 ml., 10%) and the reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 2 hrs. with occasional shaking. The contents after diluting with saturated brine solution were extracted with ether and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After evaporating the solvent, the distillation of the residue under reduced pressure afforded ethyl-2, 4, 4-trimethyl-1-acetyl-butanoate (IX), yield 2.7 g. (86.8%) b.p. $125-130^{\circ}/3$ mm. $^{35}\eta_D$ 1.4350. I.R. spectrum $1725, 1710\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ester and $\text{C}=\text{O}$), $1460, 1380\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$). Found : C, 66.02; H, 10.10; Calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$: C, 66.00; H, 10.00.

4 : 4 : 6-trimethyl-cyclohexane-1, 3-dione (II) : Potassium tertiary butoxide was prepared from potassium (1.0 g.) and tertiary butanol (75 ml.) and the excess of the tertiary butanol was removed under vacuum. The solid tertiary butoxide was powdered and placed in dry benzene, (75 ml.). To this was added the ketone (IX, 2.5 g.) and reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 hrs. It was cooled and decomposed with ice cold water. The contents were washed with benzene to remove any uncyclised product. The aqueous layer was then decomposed with ice cold hydrochloric acid (10%) and extracted with ether. Washed the ethereal layer with saturated brine solution and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removing the solvent the products solidified. It was recrystallised from petroleum ether ($60-80^{\circ}$), m.p. 130 , Lit.¹ reports m.p. $130-131^{\circ}$. It gave a brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. Found : C, 70.12; H, 9.10; Calc. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$: C, 70.10; H, 9.15.

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